

Significant review of literature on retailing emerging trends in Indian context

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Abstract:

In our modern day, digital marketing is crucial for human knowledge exchange. Digital marketing is a form of interactive advertising that is offered to customers in order to promote products or labels. Online marketing, email marketing, or web marketing is the components. Pay per click (PPC), SEO, and banner ads are increasingly a component of the digital marketing landscape. Email, RSS, phone, fax, tweeting, podcasting, video feeds, wireless text, and instant communications are all a part of digital marketing. The world of digital marketing is very diverse. It is a technique for transmitting electronic data that allows for the digital distribution of consumer goods and services. Digital marketing is becoming more and more popular in emerging trend industries worldwide. The goal of digital marketing appeals to consumers and allows them to influence the product through high-quality digital media. More people use smartphones now than they did a year ago. It can be challenging to increase sales. The sales team will benefit greatly from changes in the way website communications and advertisements are processed. Innovation in digital marketing software is more widely used since disruption is impossible without it. Opportunities abound, as do projections. For businesses like Amazon, Flipkart, eBay, Club Factory, etc., there is some internet marketing. India has 450 million internet users, according to the most recent statistics. The essay identifies the important takeaways from each topic and makes suggestions for further research needs. Additionally, it introduces new selling places. It is anticipated that it will inspire academics and retailers to carry out greater research in these and related fields in the future.

Keywords: Retailing emerging trends, Digital marketing, digital media, Innovation, website communications

Introduction:

Marketing is the process of distributing goods and services in any culture. Both firms and corporations perform these two core duties in order to uphold their obligations to their partners, including shareholders, clients, and the community at large. They are the ideal choice for the perk that economists refer to as a utility. It is a likable quality of a product or service. Shape, time, place, and property are the four different categories of services. This utility, which turns raw materials and components into finished goods and services, is produced by the corporation. Customer preferences can be categorized with the help of marketing. The true utility of forms is a result of organizations' production functions. The primary function of marketing is to define time, place, and terminology. Time and place are useful when customers discover goods or services that are offered at the time and place when they wish to purchase them. Highlight time practical online distributors available 24/7. As this facility was in operation, commercial machines were buying snacks and soft drinks. The assignment of product or facility titles at the point of payment offers ownership services. Even now, decades after the advent of a complex retail landscape, client purchasing decisions are still influenced by their needs. Despite this, new business models and technological advancements have greatly influenced the development of a new shopping experience for consumers. As a result, it's critical to get knowledge of the retailing areas where innovations are fundamentally altering the industry. Understanding

the patterns and regions where retailing will develop in the future will also result from this. Today's consumers have a wider range of options for goods and services because to the acceptance of the idea of omni channel retailing. Additionally, clients receive greater information on a range of products and services. Retailers now have the opportunity to engage with their customers by giving them relevant information in order to foster long-lasting customer engagement. Technology is quite important in this situation because it benefits both customers and retailers. By staying informed about various products and services, consumers can make wise decisions and retailers can target the right clientele. However, in practice, hardly every customer decision involves such a thorough deliberation process. Customers occasionally make hasty decisions, and the product selection and visual merchandising might affect them. This is true for both physical stores and online shops. When a customer makes a purchase from a retailer, the retailer collects all of the customer's data, including transactional, consumer, and environmental data. This enables them to forecast consumer behavior and develop more advantageous business plans that benefit them and their customers. Retailers' profitability can therefore grow as a result.

Visual Merchandising:

Consumers today are exposed to an infinite range of goods and offers on them. Retailers must balance giving their customers the best deals while also standing out in the present competitive landscape. As a result, businesses must make difficult decisions

about how to create these offers. With the channel structure in mind, this will let retailers choose how, when, and where to display their goods and related offers (within the store or on their websites). This is true for producers as well because they understand how crucial it is for customers to pay attention to their products and deals. Kahn (2017) provided techniques for streamlining assortments for consumers. They involve reducing assortments and information density, ensuring that each item corresponds to the context of the assortment, and carefully planning the spatial placement of goods. Additionally, Nordfalt et al. (2014) evaluated the impact of various merchandise orientations in their earlier work, which also looked at the value of spatial location of goods. They discovered that displaying goods vertically tended to improve customers' frequency of purchases relative to displaying goods horizontally. They continued by saying that when towels are presented vertically as opposed to diagonally, product purchases of towels increased by more than 90%. The packaging of the product, in addition to how it is displayed on the shelf or online, is an important aspect of the store's visual merchandising. Packaging typically refers to how a product is designed or shaped (Kahn, 2017). This viewpoint was further developed by Krishna et al. (2017), who attempted to analyze how packaging affected how consumers interacted with the product. Consumers' sensory experiences are influenced by the inner, middle, and outer layers of packaging, which also help them evaluate the product's physical and functional attributes. When choosing visual merchandising for their stores and websites, businesses must take into account the physical placement of their products and the sales advertising for them. The profitability of the store as a whole will be significantly impacted by this. When the sale price of the product is shown on the right side of the box rather than the left side, the sale of low involvement products is likely to increase (Suri et al., 2017).

Technological advancements in retailing:

Both retailers and customers benefit from technological improvements in the retail industry. The consumer may make better informed selections, take advantage of advantageous offers, and receive services relatively more quickly than in the past, making it easier for retailers to reach their target demographic at minimal cost (for example, through the internet). The advantages of technology for consumers and merchants have been underlined in recent research by Inman & Nikolova (2017), which will boost the company's profitability. They discussed smart shelf technology, self-checkouts, scan-and-go technologies, Que Vision, and mobile apps. For instance, a consumer can browse, take, and pay for his chosen items using self-checkout

equipment without the assistance of salespeople or cashiers. Customers will have complete control over the transaction process thanks to this, while merchants will be able to reduce labor expenses since fewer cashiers and salespeople will be needed. For shops, smartphones are a godsend in disguise. They have completely transformed today's buying experience. Consumer expectations have altered as a result of easy access to the internet, mobile apps, and other developments in this field. Additionally, this has made it simpler for retailers to reach their intended customers. For instance, scan-and-go technologies allow customers to browse the products supplied by the merchants; choose the ones that best suit their needs, and make payments using the applications of the merchants. By reducing the time it takes to scan items online, Amazon Go elevated this idea. Customers simply need to scan their iPhones when they enter the store, select their items, and then exit. The system processes the transaction automatically and keeps track of the things that are purchased or returned. A receipt is prepared and emailed to the customer as soon as the customer leaves the business, and money is immediately taken out of his account. The user must have a smartphone, an Amazon account, and the Amazon Go app in order for this entire process to be successful (Amazon, 2016). The observations that follow can be used to future research projects taking into account the literature review on technical improvements that was just mentioned.

1. Will all consumers and retailers benefit from these technological advancements?
2. Apps from merchants are likely ideal for customers who search for various discounts when buying.
3. Will small retailers use these apps, or will they have to act as pick-up and delivery locations for internet shops in order to survive?

Customer engagement:

There have been a number of studies conducted in the past on customer experience and engagement levels (Grewal, Levy, and Kumar, 2009; Puccinelli et al., 2009; Accenture, 2015; Marketing Science Institute, 2016), but none of them have looked into approaches to raise customer sense of involvement. Consciousness can increase customer involvement (Grewal et al., 2017). Grewal et al. (2017) created a hierarchal model of consumer interaction based on the idea of conscious capitalism (Mackey & Sisodia, 2017). The customer experience, emotional connection, and shared identity were presented as three levels of the three-level method for improving customer engagement. Therefore, mindful retailers can establish emotional relationships with their customers by influencing their goals and values. Three crucial elements in the realm of food retailing were found in a separate study by Wansink (2017):

the importance of signage, shop design, and personnel service. These elements help consumers choose the most practical and standardized goods to purchase. The author also suggested new signage, service components, and novel tools and procedures. In order to engage customers in both physical and online businesses, retailers should also take into account the visual concepts that are incorporated in their visual merchandising. This will foster a sense of emotional attachment to the store, which will reduce price sensitivity and enhance consumption (Roggeveen et al. 2015). Future research should focus on employee engagement because, for retailers, employee engagement would lead to customer engagement. This is because there has been a lot of research on customer experience (Grewal, Levy & Kumar, 2009; Puccinelli et al., 2009; Accenture, 2015; marketing science institute, 2016).

Role of big data in retailing:

Retail firms have always been inundated with data, but owing to improper data management, they were unable to use it effectively. Retailers have recently begun using choices for organizing data, computational systems, and analytical systems for the business due to advancements in technology. Retailers were able to manage their problems thanks to big data and analytical systems. In terms of customer, product, place, time, and channel, Bradlow et al (2017) illustrations of big data measurements and recommendations for strategically. Utilize these data to increase price and maximize sales. The data gathered from various sources, including loyalty cards, websites, mobile apps, and business systems, has also been organized. Big data is therefore assisting researchers as well as retailers to better comprehend the customers. Researchers are conducting field research and experiments to evaluate the basis between independent (pricing, display, assortment, etc.) and dependent variables as a result of the introduction of big data (sales volume, profitability etc.).

Criteria for store selection:

The primary variables taken into account for site analysis include competition, store performance, demographics, and retail features. In the section that follows, a review of the literature has been done for each category with the goal of assisting future researchers in carrying out studies based on store performance.

Store Performance:

One of the most crucial factors in choosing the store's location is performance. It is equally crucial to take into account the factors that influence the store's performance. The ability to estimate performance goals affects the quality of the selection criteria for the store placement model. The store's profitability (Walter & McKenzie, 1988),

market share (Durvasula et al., 1992), demand (Igene & Lusch, 1980; Berman & Evans, 2010; Li & Liu, 2012), and price elasticity (Hoch et al., 1995) are common ways that these goals are created. Therefore, in order for stores to enter the neighborhood and receive the most utility, the aforementioned procedures for selecting the store location are crucial.

Demographics:

The placement of the store is heavily influenced by the characteristics of the local population. Retailers can use demographic data to determine whether the local population is representative of their intended market (Hasty & Reardon, 1997; Berman & Evan, 2010). Some clients' consumption patterns are especially challenging to change due to their financial circumstances or ingrained habits (Redinbaugh, 1987). As a result, it has been found that while picking a location for a store, retailers must take into account the local population's shopping preferences. Therefore, for retail managers, the most crucial factor in determining a possible shop location is the market's demographic makeup (Hasty & Reardon, 1997).

Store features:

The qualities of the retail space have a direct impact on how competitive it is. To gain a competitive edge in the market, retailers should concentrate on these traits. The decision to locate a store depends on factors such as accessibility (simply locating a store), store image characteristics (such as merchandise assortments, atmospherics, etc.), and related prices. Many research have talked about the accessibility when choosing the sites for stores. In order for customers to enter the store for shopping easily, it is important to pay attention to roads and parking facilities given that many customers commute using their own vehicles. The accessibility of the store has an impact on its sales potential, either favorably or unfavorably (Redinbaugh, 1987). Additionally, before implementing any modification to enhance the store's reputation, retailers should consider how it may affect sales. With the aid of new and improved layout and allocation procedures, improvements in product selections or store ambiance affect not only the flow of revenues but also the expenses (Igene & Lusch, 1980). Finally, while choosing a site for a business, retailers should take costs into account as well as store performance. The costs that are taken into account when making decisions include those related to the building, rent, store renovations, etc (Irwing, 1986).

Competition:

While looking for suitable locations for new stores, it is crucial for retailers to get an understanding of their competitive environment (Reinartz & Kumar, 1999). According to observations, differences in pricing elasticity between retailers are caused by

competitive variables (Hoch et al., 1995). There may be direct or indirect competition. In the case of direct competition, a new store will attempt to compete with existing stores that already sell the same products in order to increase their market share (Durvasula et al., 1992), whereas in the case of indirect competition (stores offering dissimilar products), each retailer will attempt to compete with the other in order to gain a larger share of customers' expenditure (Redinbaugh, 1987). Therefore, it is crucial to consider the competition when picking the location of the store. The choice of store site should also take into account factors like the distance from the competitor's store, the number of possible competitors, the strength of the competition, etc. Retailers can learn more about the success of a business at a specific location by looking at the aforementioned factors. Therefore, when assessing the performance of the store, managers should be mindful of elements that are related to the location of the store. However, tastes in retail store sites evolve with time. Due to potential competition invasion, a place that originally appears profitable could lose its allure. Ingene & Lusch (1980) added that demographic shifts will promote uncertainty in satisfying customer demands and wants. Retailers must take into account the evolving competitive landscape, and to do this, they must be aware of the variables that affect shop performance (Ghosh & Craig, 1983). Retailers are recommended to conduct timely research on issues influencing the performance of their stores in order to position their businesses in the changing consumer environment.

Future trends in retailing:

Because of changes in consumer behavior and technological improvement, the retail industry is developing more quickly. Big data and the idea of Omni channel commerce are now crucial for handling competition. Even more recent technology,

such as smart devices, mediated or virtual reality, and artificial intelligence, is essential to the future of retail (Deloitte, 2016). Future study must address the "internet of things" notion in order to clarify how consumer behavior will be influenced and to comprehend the function of front-line managers. For instance, smart homes and smart automobiles are being developed to gather pertinent information or data like when to order the essential items maintained in refrigerators (or any other appliance) or when the next service on the car is due. Therefore, it's crucial to investigate whether it will boost customers' involvement with store owners or retailers or whether it will decrease it and usher in a new era of machine-to-machine communication. Applications based on artificial intelligence (AI) are also in high demand and may positively affect customer spending at both online and physical establishments. Artificial intelligence (AI)-based responses will be useful in obtaining information about the products, their placement in the store, their features, and will also provide suggestions for further items that would complement the items already purchased. As a result, customers will be better educated and more engaged than they were previously. However, in order to provide service staff with the high level of information that is stored in AI applications; their jobs will need to be rearranged. Companies are experimenting with autonomous vehicles that are driven by AI-based technologies. Many manufacturers and merchants are attempting to take advantage of the potential presented by robotics and drone technology advancement (Van Doorn et al., 2016). Amazon recently announced plans to strengthen its current delivery system by adding a drone delivery option. Such applications provide access for this field's researchers to learn more about the benefits and side effects of these distribution methods.

Above image showing emerging trends of organized retailing in India: A shared vision of consumers and retailers

Current marketing trends:

Here are the 11 most up to date developments in your marketing strategy that you want to integrate:

Content marketing:

Content marketing, one of the more established communication methods, is first on the list and continues to be a top option. Long-form web content, like blog postings, continues to be popular because it gives people what they need in response to their searches and educates them. The audience for content marketing must be those who consume useful material. In order to click it, you want to search for company keywords and use your content to respond to consumer search inquiries.

Semantic keyword research:

Both content marketing and the usage of keywords to enhance search engine optimization (SEO) are not new. When choosing keywords for your sites, you must be sure to take the user's search intention into account. The study of the semantic keyword is based on this hypothesis.

It's not necessary to use this identical phrase in writing that solely promotes your lawnmower accessories if readers search for "how to repair an arm's length." You need to have information on lawnmower repairs on your website. If the user's search is not compatible, your website's search results won't be listed highly. Use the term to examine what content already uses the supplied keyword to take into account Google's search objective. The best content ought to provide you a clear idea of what to imitate.

Ranking for position zero:

Making the search results more thorough is one of SEO's objectives. To appear first in the search results, the majority of businesses aim for the "null spot." Position Zero, also known as the featured snippet, is a box that appears at the top of the search results. This is a very appealing location to click, not least since the click through rate (CTR) for the first organic result decreases by 8% if a highlighted snippet is present. You will achieve this by including succinct, direct responses to queries in your contents.

Personalization:

Customers want personalized advertising in 2023 that is tailored to their unique traits and interests. Since too many firms are competing for their attention, they don't waste time reading information that doesn't pertain to their wants. One of the simplest methods to do this is to send targeted email advertisements. Personalization increases email exchange by 10%. To send emails that are tailored to your subscribers' needs, you will segment your subscriber base. To make your emails more personalized, the recipient's name is frequently added. Although it's a simple tap, whether or not someone wants to interact with your material can have a major impact.

Video marketing:

In today's marketing environment, images may have the strongest audiences. If you've ever tried to read a book or do a job while your TV is in front of you, you know how difficult it is to keep your eyes from wandering into the fast action and flashing graphics there. The same phrase is used in commercials. For

instance, it would be handy for a customer to whistle via text or image-based advertising as they browse through their social networking page, but a video playback would be far more likely to catch their eyes as soon as it surfaces. Videos will actually increase your email marketing's click rate by a staggering 300 percent, making it one of the top publicity trends for 2020. To include videos in your marketing campaign, you can submit Facebook autoplay video ads or check for any YouTube stockpile advertising.

Voice search optimization:

In 2010, the majority of Google users entered terms into the search bar using a computer keyboard. By 2015, they were using the keyboard on their phone. By 2020, there were more voice searchers as a result of these shifting marketing trends. Nowadays, thanks to technology like Amazon Echo and Google Home, individuals constantly speak out loud in search of a wave of sentences-long keywords. More than 55% of users now use voice search to look up nearby businesses.

Shoppable posts:

Although social media has long been a hub for advertisements, one of the most significant recent developments in marketing is the rise of online commerce. Nowadays, a lot of social media platforms offer services like Instagram Shopping and the Facebook Marketplace that let you buy things directly from the app without visiting a retailer's website. To set this up, you must first have a company account on the preferred website. Following that, you may set up shopping posts and begin adding products to your account.

Social media stories:

Another trend in today's social networking advertising is stories. Snapchat-produced story images or videos are only viewed for a short period of time before quickly spreading to other websites. You have the ideal opportunity to profit from lost user anxiety thanks to Stories. For a while, the stories disappear, viewers are more obligated to converse with them, but the content does not disregard them. You can compel more customers to use the sales to buy your products if you use these stories to trade sales figures.

Browser pushes notifications:

On occasion, visitors to the website begin to leave before making a purchase or signing up. Sending the customer a final contact request to unsubscribe from your business is appropriate in these circumstances. Push notifications have been around for a long, but they are still widely used today. A user can choose to activate a box with an email list, for example, when they move their mouse to a click away from your website. In the end, this will provide you more lead.

Website security:

Today's world places a greater emphasis than ever on online security. The requirement for security is significantly larger in places where people trade financial information, and whether or not your website has an online store, you'd want to make sure that your customers feel at ease using it. Making sure that the proper safety precautions are taken is still a smart idea. It's ideal to have certified certificates of protection from organizations like PayPal or VeriSign, so you should at least verify that your website is using the HTTPS protocol because failing to do so could result in a ranking penalty from Google.

Conclusion:

Customers' buying habits will continue to be impacted by the latest retail trends. Additionally, it will help them choose the best channel, products, and services before they make the actual buy. Retailers are attempting to adopt the Omni channel retailing notion as the ideas of online and physical commerce merge. The latest technological trends and advancements enable clients to make wise selections quickly, leaving them feeling confident and immensely satisfied. On the other hand, retailers should embrace this cutting-edge technology to improve customer interaction. It will be beneficial to undertake additional research by continuing to explore this field in order to achieve that. Also India is undergoing a tremendous digitization revolution for its citizens. More Indian buyers search the internet to discover the greatest bargain from sellers. Search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing, content integration, software automation, electronic commerce, campaign marketing, and social network marketing are some of the technologically sophisticated digital marketing strategies that are growing in popularity. We are all connected today thanks to the work done by Facebook and smartphones, which are used to attract customers via a global network. Digital marketing is economical and has a significant impact on industry.

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